

ENVIRONMENTAL THROUGH SPORTS TOURISM EVENTS IN STUDENTS PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF CULTURE DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

Tourism, sports and material, cultural heritage, ecology in our republic It is important to train personnel and support the development of science in these areas attention is being paid. This is to improve the health of the environment based on the development of sports tourism requires. This article is about sports tourism activities of students in our country together with the increase of interests, serves the development of ecological culture.

Scientists have focused on sports tourism and the uniqueness of walks, its social life and its place and importance in the life of an individual, in the culture of a healthy lifestyle of a person scientifically and practically studied. Features and diversity of sports tourism and hiking scientists who conducted research on the issues: R. Kasimov, tourism, the value and necessity of walking formation of social behavior, determining one's place in society, communication they emphasize the importance of being able to regulate their actions in the process. In our opinion, the state educational standard and curricula of general secondary education in the content of the following methods with environmental knowledge, skills, skills and competencies enrichment is appropriate. Including: service to the development of environmental culture among students in the process of sports tourism inculcation of knowledge, skills, qualifications and competences into the content of education;

- an opportunity to apply ecological knowledge in the content of academic subjects in practice enrichment with practical assignments (transition from theory or discussion to practice);
- the content of subjects in the educational programs related to waste in the Republic implementation, generation of waste, damage to nature and their elimination Enrichment with issues such as factors;
- enriching the content of the subjects of mathematics and the basics of economic knowledge with specific economic and ecological issues related to savings;
- to foresee the results of the student's own and others' activities and geography, mathematics, biology, basic sciences of economic knowledge in order to teach assessment knowledge, skills, competences related to ecological assessment and ecological forecasting (prognosis). and introducing competencies in accordance with the age of students starting from the lower grades (7-8-9). to go

- environmental knowledge in general secondary education depends on the age, physical capabilities of students and taking into account the psychological characteristics, it is organized into sections of classes;
- teaching pedagogical principles such as "from simple to complex", "integrality and continuity". based on the combination of theoretical and practical knowledge, students' ecological culture and becoming a target system that ensures the gradual formation of physical education need.

To the theoretical foundations of ecology in the process of sports tourism in the general secondary education system related knowledge and knowledge aimed at forming ecological culture and ecological education, imparting skills, qualifications and competencies on the basis of coherence in the content of existing academic subjects and should represent a whole complex (not mutually exclusive). Development of environmental culture in the process of sports tourism in the general secondary education system is carried out in the following stages:

1. primary education (grades I-IV);
 2. general secondary education (grades I-XI).
1. To develop environmental culture in the process of sports tourism in primary education it is appropriate to pay attention to the basics of literacy, knowledge and skills.
 2. In the elementary grades, students additionally study ecology and acquisition of the following knowledge, skills and qualifications related to the field of environmental protection condition:
 - a) objects of nature protection (land, underground resources, water, flora and fauna to preserve the world and the air of the atmosphere) like the apple of an eye;
 - b) the need to save and conserve water;
 - c) the importance of atmospheric air and the need to protect it;
 - g) to have information about land resources, soil and rock, minerals;
 - d) The "Red Book" of the Republic of Uzbekistan, including the most rare animals and plant species;
 - e) waste, the nature of household waste, their placement and only specified thrown into places;
 - j) about the beautiful and unique nature of Uzbekistan;
 - z) his work in preserving the nature of the village (city) where he lives to have information about the nature of Tiroki and large nature reserves in Uzbekistan and it is desirable to obtain information about the effects of nature on the human body.

While sports tourism occupies a certain place in the lives of adults, it is important for students has Tourism to the legendary tourist regions of our republic, mountains and valleys, forests, Riverside and lakeside tourism is important for human health today is important. These types of sports are the manifestation of the students' identity improvement is a method that serves this purpose. Theory of sports tourism and hiking to be developed It is also important for the development of pedagogy. In this respect, the 7th grade physical sports tourism, walks when students complete didactic tasks in education classes along with perfecting the technique, moral qualities through the subjects of tourism, walks they perfect themselves. In the 8th grade, it is recommended to conduct tourism, walks, mainly in the final

part of the lesson. Because tourism and walks integrate lessons. Sports tourism and walking are separate it is necessary to pay attention. With students of this age, it is mostly simple and moderately complex tourism and walks are held. If the students are sufficiently prepared, even more so more complex, that is, sports tourism and walks are organized and held in teams. And in the 9th grade, the basis for instilling moral qualities in students through these exercises is created. they develop a sense of responsibility. This is the case of participants in sports tourism and walks increases responsibility. Sports tours and walks are good enough to be fun and impressive It requires agility, dexterity and strength, physical fitness, and at the same time these characteristics improves. Physical education classes often consist of various sports tours and walks. The teacher conducts sports tours and marches for 7-9 grade students not to forget that their characteristics are expressed by the faster growth of their organism, and therefore tourism and walks held in classes for should be given in a coordinated manner. In the process of sports tourism and hiking, students are subjected to excessive physical activity and the teacher should treat each of them accordingly. The volume of sports tourism used by students comes from educational tasks comes out. Sports tourism held in these classes is organized and conducted it will be full of content. In the main part of the lesson, students are not complicated some to the preparatory part of the lesson to prepare for studying the eco-object in the direction exercises can be included (focusing on birds, flowers). At the end of the quarter, lessons using the developed methodology, mainly sports tourism, pre-analysis is carried out after assessment of inspection regulations. The lesson is more thorough to achieve the division, as well as to strengthen the acquired skills and to the students at the end of the main part of sports tourism and walks in order to increase the top Shiriq can be used.

The requirements of the educational programs are specific goals and tasks for the students of the 7th grade puts In such a sharing, physical education classes and physical education of sports tourism it is natural for him to take a leading place in other trainings held by Boisha. Sports though even if tourism is included in the training, it is an acquired movement in different types of sports improvement and strengthening of skills is envisaged. So, sports tourism during the transfer, it is necessary to monitor its implementation with special attention. It goes without saying that sports tourism included in the lesson will help master one or another element should consist of exercises. The task of tourism and walks held in the final part of the training is good reduce stress on muscles, breathing and blood to relax and improve mood is to calm the circulation somewhat. Mountain slopes, forests, river banks, tours to the shores of the lake in the implementation of tasks in the final part of the lesson will help. Well-chosen sports tourism is an important condition for the success of education. These composition, age characteristics, as well as physical characteristics of the participants in preparing for the transfer taking into account their preparations, it is necessary to determine the main tasks of the training. The teacher should know exactly how the training will be conducted when choosing sports tourism need If sports tourism is held in winter, it will activate students and a more active route that evenly distributes the physical task should be chosen. Sports if tourism is held in spring, then work is done according to the season. The most important thing is in seasonal walks it is necessary to follow anthropogenic and natural

ecofacts. Pay attention to the following pedagogical conditions when conducting sports tourism and walks should focus on:

- determine the composition of those who go on sports tourism;
- interview with parents of sports tourism participants;
- necessary sports equipment, equipment, for example, rope with a diameter of 8 cm, wool, tape, rubber balls (rubber balls do not lose their tension at high temperatures stored in a cool place for 1 m long sports sticks, rope, belts, flags, felts, hammers, first aid kits, every student should be exposed to the sun to avoid eye pain must have safety glasses;
- the route of sports tourism should be flat, free of thorns, stones, broken glass must be kept clean;
- there should be no strangers on the track during training. Because they are distracting the students and forcing them to overwork they reach;
- it is necessary to use natural objects and things on the highway. In addition to tourism the following eco-hygiene rules must be observed during the transfer:

a) The clothes worn in sports tourism events should be light, not making it difficult to walk necessary;

b) In the summer, you should take a bath after sports tourism. Distribution and installation of teaching equipment, participation in sports tourism events assistants to monitor the implementation of the rules and take into account the results can choose. The assistant is the future organizer of sports tourism. Assisted sports tourism should treat its participants objectively. Experience in sports tourism in large areas it is appropriate for the students to be assistants to the teacher. He is in good health the power of students who are not and who are temporarily exempted from physical education classes in sports tourism can participate as much as possible. Activities without waiting for students to get tired of sports tourism it should be completed depending on how much it affects them. How long does sports tourism last? the number and age of participants, the nature and image of sports tourism, technical equipment amount, weather and distribution will depend on the condition of the route. Regulation of sports tourism depending on the enthusiasm of the participants of sports tourism and management, it is necessary to know its purpose, the meaning and importance of its rules. Students compliance with the rules of sports tourism should always be in the focus of the teacher's attention. Because compliance with the rules of ecotourism is of great educational value. Teacher to record the mistakes of tourists without haste and thoughtfully and every the participant of sports tourism should be obliged to obey the general eco-rules. It is important to prevent mistakes and abuses made by sports tourists should be considered with importance. Especially for the participants of group sports tourism it is necessary to monitor with sensitivity that it is the same for the participants. The most important condition for the successful growth of sports tourism is caution, solidarity, sensitivity, discipline and strict adherence to them. Self-development of environmental culture in students at sports tourism events how they behave depends more on the physical education teacher. Sports tourism is mandatory begins with a gesture (command, clapping or clapping, waving a hand or a flag). The teacher made sure that all participants understood the content of sports tourism and went to a more comfortable place points after he is satisfied that he is settled. "Conditional limits are set in advance and necessary manuals for sports tourism and hiking to

the rules of sports tourism and hiking it must be given and put in place. Leader sports tourism and carefully monitors and manages the activities of tourism participants. From this In addition, it additionally explains some rules and methods during sports tourism.

Corrections, reprimands and comments that do not interfere with the progress of sports tourism or it it should be said in a way that does not stop. If most of the participants of sports tourism What is the appropriate guidance or course of action if making the same mistake?

Sports tourism can be stopped to demonstrate its implementation. But shout it or sharply It is not appropriate to stop with a gesture. The teacher is conscious and clear about the rules of the students should get used to doing it. This habit is of great importance in teaching them discipline. to educate students to know their duty and take responsibility for their actions, helps to develop self-control and perseverance.

So, as a conclusion, it can be said that students are the leaders of sports tourism not limited to being interested only in the achieved results, but also in the process of sports tourism in them paying serious attention to creating a sense of self-pleasure and pleasure must.

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